

MAIN DIRECTIONS IN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN POLICY OF THE REPUBLIC OF KOREA

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6620714>

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Annotation: "Taehan Minguk" means the Republic of Korea in Korean. Korean soy originated from the name of the ancient Koryo dynasty (918-1392) in the territory. And the name Koryo goes even earlier to the state of Koguryo. The Republic of Korea is located in the southern part of the Korean Peninsula, therefore it is called South Korea in an informal language. The Korean coast is washed by the Yellow Sea in the West, the Japanese sea in the East, and the Korean Strait in the south and the North China Sea. In the North, Korea borders on the people's Democratic Republic. The territory of the country consists mainly of mountainous areas, the plain is thirty percent.

Keywords: South Korea, politics, Government, Seoul, cooperation, history.

String-like vine branches

Ancient studies suggest that people came to the territory of the Korean Peninsula seventy thousand years ago. In the khamgyon-Pukto, Pyongyang-Namdo, Kyongido and Chhunchkhon-Pukto regions, labor weapons of the most ancient stone age were found. The most ancient pottery samples date back to 8000 years BC.

The first state in the history of Korea is ancient Choson (Ko Choson). This association was first mentioned in the sources of the IV-III century BC. The state of Choson was founded at the beginning as an association of tribes, only by the IV century BC it became a centralized state. When this saltanat was in crisis, tribal associations Makhhan, Chinhaan and Pyonghan arose. At the beginning of the century BC, the territory of the Korean peninsula was dominated by Silla, Pekche and Koguryo, and in the North By The Parke state. The Silla Tribal Association occupied Pekche and Koguria in 676 year,

as a result of which the United Silla State appeared. This saltanate received the name Koryo in 936 year and ruled until 1392 year. LITERATURE REVIEW

From 1231 the Mongols began to organize an attack on Koryo, and after twenty-five years of Wars, The Kingdom of Koryo became vassalga. In the middle of the XIV century, the Mongolian rule began to decline, and King Konmin began to act independently. In 1392 year, the chief commander of Koryo, Lee Son Ge, abolished the Kingdom and founded the Choson state. The capital of the country is Hanson – now moved to Seoul. In the XV century, the Korean alphabet-khangil was created. And the kingdom of Chason 1627-1636 years, the Kingdom of Sin was under the hand. In 1895 year practically passed under Japanese rule. In 1897 year, Van Kojon re-conquered the imperial throne, but he could not gain any power at all. After the Russo-Japanese war of 1904-1905, Japan again became dependent on Korea, and in 1910 year completely conquered it. Due to the defeat in the Second World War, Japan's dominance in Korea was terminated. The northern part of Korea was occupied by the former Union, the southern part by the United States.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

In 1948, the Republic of Korea and the Democratic People's Republic of Korea were formed. The war of 1950-1953, which took place between the two countries, completely destroyed the military ties.

In the Republic of Korea, the dictatorial regime reigned for forty years. Before Lee Sin Man (rolled up in 1960 year), then Pak Chjon Xi (killed in 1979 year) reigned power. Between the years 198-87 Chon Du Hwan became president. The referendum in 1987 year approved a new constitution. This Constitution, which entered into force on February 25, 1988, introduced a direct presidential election instead of a multi-stage election, the rights of the Parliament were abolished, the powers of the president were limited, the term of office was reduced from seven to five years, the press was strengthened.

Democratic liberal Party candidate Kim Yen Sam won the presidential election held in December 1992. His motto was " reforms in the conditions of stability", which carried out a number of reforms. Since that time, the state was headed by several presidents, democracy remained the main criterion of governance.

National holidays: 15 August – Korean Freedom Day (1945); 3 October- the day of foundation of the state.

Since 1992, Uzbekistan and 29 janvar have been cooperating in various fields.

Member of the UN since September 17, 1991.

Economic. In the 1960s, Korea was one of the poorest countries in the region. It is now one of the developed, powerful industrialized countries. Like other developed countries, the sphere of services here is considered to be the dominant branch of the economy. It accounts for two-thirds of the gross domestic product.

He is a leader in the world of ship production. Forty-five percent share of the world market is accounted for by Korea. The automotive industry is also developed. There are a number of large enterprises with Korean investment in Uzbekistan.

Residents. The main part of the population consists of Koreans. There are about a hundred thousand Chinese, they moved mainly from Japan, Malaysia, India and the Philippines.

Schoolchildren are obliged to know Korean and English in order to study in the middle and upper classes. After passing to the upper class, it is also possible to choose one of the Chinese, Japanese, French, German, Russian, Spanish and Arabic for further study.

Religious. According to the 2005 census, 46,5 percent of the population did not consider himself related to any religion, while 29,3 percent said he was a Christian. 18,3 percent of Christians are protestant, 10,9 percent are Catholic. 22,8 percent of the population are Buddhists.

The number of Muslims in the country is more than forty thousand. Most of them are immigrants from South and South-East Asia. In recent times, even among the representatives of the local population, those who accept Islam are increasing. The largest mosque in Korea is located in Seoul's Itevon theme. In all the rest of the big cities there are mosques.

The first Muslims to Korea came in the VI–IX centuries. They were Chinese merchants. This country is considered a closed country in religious matters. This situation continued until the XIX century. However, while not routine, Koreans became familiar with Islamic Science and culture. In the 60-ies of the last century, Muslims began to multiply in the country. In 1980, a group of Korean Muslims first went on a pilgrimage.

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